

OUTDOOR ACCESS FOR PULLETS

Early outdoor access **reduces fear, increases the likelihood of ranging as adults** and **limits injurious pecking**.

WELFARE INDICATORS

TO ASSESS WHEN PULLETS ARE READY
TO ACCESS THE OUTDOOR AREA

The most relevant indicator:
Plumage coverage

Good plumage coverage requires **full grown adult feathers**, without bald areas.

Body weight

Can be an indicator but recommended cut-off depend on genetics.

Mortality, diseases, health problems

In case of need, a veterinarian should analyse these indicators before allow outdoor access.

Weather conditions

Access could be delayed in case of adverse weather conditions.

Pullets should be ready to access the outdoor **AROUND 8-10 WEEKS OF AGE** (and no later than 12 weeks).

HOW TO OPTIMIZE PULLETS' FREE RANGING?

ACCESSIBLE POPHOLES

Wide and large with an open view, little light contrast and a dry access

RANGE FREE OF DISEASE RISKS

No soiled water, soil pollution, garbage... that can be source of diseases

MAJORITY OF OUTDOOR RANGE COVERED BY VARIOUS TYPE OF VEGETATION

- Attract animal to the outdoor
- Better expression of natural behaviors (pecking for insects, hiding from predators...)
- Improve animal distribution (reduced parasitic contamination, phosphate accumulation...)

NATURAL OR ARTIFICIAL SHELTER

(starting near to the house)

- Safety from predators
- Weather protection (sun, rain, wind)

ENRICHMENT MATERIAL

Increase of behavioral opportunities (grass, foraging sources, dust bathing substrates...)

For any questions or suggestions regarding this document, please contact

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